

MICROMECHANICAL DEFORMATIONS IN PARTICULATE FILLED POLYMERS: THE EFFECT OF ADHESION

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SUMMARY

Debonding is the dominating micromechanical deformation mode in particulate filled polymers, which depends on particle size and interfacial adhesion. PP composites were prepared with different fillers having a wide range of particle characteristics. Debonding was studied by acoustic emission to determine the factors influencing sound development and the effect of interfacial interaction on it.

Keywords: particulate filled polymers, micromechanical deformation, debonding, interfacial adhesion, acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

Particulate filled polymer, short fiber reinforced composites and polymer blends are used in large quantities in all fields of life. Most of these materials have heterogeneous structure and they are used in structural applications. Under the effect of external load inhomogeneous stress distribution develops around the inclusions, which induces local deformation processes. The dominating deformation is usually debonding in particulate filled and short fiber reinforced polymers, but other micromechanical deformation processes were also detected in such materials [1]. These processes can be followed by various techniques. Volume strain measurements can follow changes in the volume of the specimen during deformation. Apart from shear yielding most micromechanical deformation mechanisms are accompanied by volume increase, thus the method cannot distinguish among them.

Another technique frequently used for the measurement and analysis of micromechanical deformations is acoustic emission, the detection of signals developing during the deformation of the specimen. Most micromechanical deformation events emit sound which can be picked up by appropriate microphones. The characteristics of the sound waves is closely related to the event emitting it, thus the analysis of the various parameters might offer valuable information about the mechanism of the deformation process. The number of events (hits), their amplitude, frequency or energy are the most often recorded quantities used in such analysis. The detailed analysis of such signals led to the identification of four different micromechanical deformation processes in wood flour reinforced PP composites [2]. The matrix deformed mainly by

shear yielding, while the dominating deformation process depended on the strength of interfacial adhesion in the composites. Mainly debonding occurred when adhesion was poor, but also fiber pull-out took place for longer particles. When adhesion was increased by the addition of functionalized polymer (MAPP), fiber fracture became the dominating mechanism and only limited debonding occurred at the same time.

The approach is frequently used for the study of the deformation mechanism of fiber reinforced polymers. Fiber related processes, especially the fracture of fibers is of sufficiently high energy thus the detection of signals does not create any problem. However, in particulate filled polymers the energy of the signals is much smaller thus occasionally no sound is detected during deformation. The study of a large number of particulate and short fiber reinforced composites indicated that the main factors influencing sound generation are the particle size of the filler and interfacial adhesion. However, the exact effect of these factors was and in some extent is still unclear. In some cases we observed that increasing the adhesion by surface modification led to the disappearance of signals (PP/PMMA composites), while in other cases increased adhesion resulted in a large number of strong signals (PP/CaCO₃/MAPP). Additionally, the dimensions of the specimens tested also influenced sound generation in some cases. In view of these observations, the goal of the project was to find a general correlation among filler characteristics, interfacial adhesion, the extent of debonding and the evolution of acoustic signals.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Tipplon H 543 polypropylene homopolymer produced by TVK, Hungary was used as matrix for all composites. Various fillers were studied with different particle sizes and surface modifications. Glass beads were obtained from Potters Industries, the size of the particles covered the range from 10 to 203 μm average size. Altogether five grades were used in the study. Various surface modification techniques were applied to change interfacial adhesion; stearic acid coating, MAPP, treatment with an aminosilane [(3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane] and the combination of silane treatment and MAPP. Another type of filler used was CaCO₃. Four Omyacarb grades including Omyacarb 2 GU, 15 GU, 40 GU and 130 GU were added to the polymer in different amounts. Interfacial interactions were modified by stearic acid coating and by the addition of functionalized polymer (MAPP). Two types of composite series were prepared. In most cases filler content changed from 0 to 0.3 volume fraction in 0.05 volume fraction steps. In other series the extent of surface modification was changed at 15 vol% filler content. A cross-linked PMMA model filler was also prepared and studied. Its preparation and characteristics are described in detail elsewhere [3]. The components were homogenized in a Brabender W 50 EH internal mixer at 190 °C, 50 rpm for 10 min, and then the melt was compression molded into 1 mm thick plates at the same temperature using a Fontijne SRA 100 machine.

The mechanical properties of the composites were characterized by tensile testing using an Instron 5566 apparatus with 10 mm/min cross-head speed and 80 mm gauge length. Acoustic emission signals were recorded with a Sensophone AED 40/4 apparatus. Volume increase was followed by measuring changes in the thickness of the specimen with an optical extensometer. The 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

system Aramis was used for the determination of volume strain. After deformation and debonding, the structure of the composites was studied by SEM. Micrographs were taken from fracture surfaces using a JEOL 6380 LA. Specimens were removed from the tensile testing machine after a given deformation, notched, immersed into liquid nitrogen and broken in order to create the fracture surfaces.

BACKGROUND

Several research groups studied micromechanical deformation processes in particulate filled and short fiber reinforced polymers [4-6]. Most agree that the dominating micromechanical deformation process is debonding in these materials. Two groups derived models which define the factors determining debonding stress [4,5]. The models differ somewhat in their assumptions, but the approach is very similar and yields the following equation for debonding stress:

$$\sigma^D = -C_1\sigma^T + C_2\sqrt{\frac{W_{AB}E}{R_f}} \quad (1)$$

where σ^D and σ^T are debonding and thermal stress, respectively, W_{AB} the reversible work of adhesion, E the Young's modulus of the matrix, R_f the radius of the particles, while C_1 and C_2 are constants [5]. The equation indicates that the stress necessary to initiate debonding depends on the properties of the components, i.e. on the stiffness of the matrix and on the particle size of the filler, as well as on interfacial adhesion. The modulus of the matrix is kept constant in this study, but particle size and interfacial interaction is changed in a wide range.

The correlation has several implications for expected changes in the acoustic emission behavior of the studied composites. Debonding stress increases with decreasing particle size, thus we may assume that also the energy of debonding would increase, which may result in increased number and intensity of the signals. Surface modification resulting in increased adhesion should point into the same direction, although very strong adhesion may prevent the debonding of the particles. On the other hand, decreased adhesion, e.g. treatment with stearic acid may lead to very easy debonding and to the loss of sound. Similarly, we may also assume that below a certain particle size debonding does not take place at all, thus acoustic emission signals will not be recorded at all. Changes in the number and intensity of acoustic emission signals were observed indeed in line with the prediction of the model. However, the direction of these changes was sometimes quite unexpected and needed further investigation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results will be discussed in several sections below. First examples are given for the different behavior of the composites prepared then the effect of the investigated factors on sound generation is presented in detail. The relation of the intensity of the signals to adhesion is shown in the subsequent section and finally the consequence of

micromechanical deformations on the performance of the composite is considered briefly at the end of the paper.

Acoustic Emission, Sound Generation

The acoustic emission testing of a composite may yield very different number of signals with widely differing characteristics. Some composites do not give any sound during their deformation, while others emit as much as 10,000 signals or more. The number of signals depends mainly on the factors mentioned already above, i.e. particle size and adhesion, but other factors may also influence it. In order to demonstrate these relationships the results of two measurements are presented in Fig. 1. The acoustic signals detected during the tensile testing of a composite containing neat, uncoated CaCO_3 particles with $36\ \mu\text{m}$ average particle size is shown in Fig. 1a together with the corresponding stress vs. deformation trace. We can see that the number of signals is small and although their amplitude covers a relatively wide range, it remains relatively small as well. On the other hand, increasing adhesion by the introduction of MAPP leads to a considerable increase both in the number of signals and in their amplitude.

Fig. 1 Effect of adhesion on the number of acoustic emission signals detected in PP/ CaCO_3 composites. a) $36\ \mu\text{m}$, neat; b) MAPP. (O) individual signals.

The results presented in Fig. 1 are difficult to understand. The small number of signals detected in the composite containing the neat filler cannot be explained by the small particle size of the filler and the lack of debonding, since particles of this size was shown to debond very easily. Accordingly, extensive debonding must occur and the lack of signals can be a result of weak interaction. This explanation is supported by the fact that increased adhesion leads to a larger number of signals, indicating that adhesion and debonding stress play an important role in sound generation. Apparently, the debonding of the particles, or some other micromechanical deformation process, generates a considerable number of acoustic events when adhesion increases.

The effect of particle size is equally interesting. Composites containing two of our fillers, both glass and CaCO_3 with the smallest particle size, did not give any signal at all. The plausible explanation is again the absence of debonding. Debonding stress (see Eq. 1) might be larger than the yield stress or tensile strength of the composite thus the dominating deformation cannot be debonding in this case. The number of acoustic signals increases with particle size for both fillers, but glass beads with the very large, 200 μm particle size are not very active and the number of acoustic events is smaller again than at intermediate sizes. Acoustic activity obviously depends on particle size, but not in a very simple manner.

The particle size distribution of some of the CaCO_3 fillers studied is presented in Fig. 2. All the distributions are quite broad, they cover at least one order of magnitude in size, but occasionally almost three decades. The smallest particles are somewhat larger than 0.2 μm , while the largest ones are close to 700 μm . A similar range is covered also by the glass beads used. Considering the wide range of particle sizes involved, we may assume that some of the particles do not debond on the one hand, while others do not give sound upon debonding for some reason, on the other. If the limiting size for sound development is in the range of 10-20 μm , it is clear that we cannot expect the filler with an average particle size of 2.9 μm to give sound and the same applies to the glass bead with the average size of 10 μm .

Fig. 2 Particle size distribution of some of the CaCO_3 fillers used in the study.

Figure 3 offers a better view about the effect of the two most important factors on the number of acoustic emission signals detected for the various composites. The average number of hits seems to increase slightly with particle size. The value obtained for the glass particles with 71 μm average size is larger than expected (see symbol \circ , ~3000 hits), which needs further explanation. It is interesting to note, that both the CaCO_3 fillers and the glass beads seem to fall onto the same correlation, which indicates that interfacial adhesion is rather similar in the two cases.

Fig. 3 Effect of particle size and adhesion on the number of acoustic events detected.

The effect of interfacial adhesion on the number of signals detected is even more interesting. The treatment of CaCO₃ with stearic acid was shown to decrease interfacial adhesion between the filler and the matrix [7]. Decreased adhesion led to smaller number of detected signals. On the other hand, increased adhesion resulted in a drastic increase in the number of detected hits, it increased from 60 to 1200 for the smaller and from 500 to more than 10,000 for the largest particles. Obviously, adhesion plays an even more important role in the development of acoustic emission signals than size. However, a question remains open yet. Debonding stress must be relative large for the small particles even without any treatment and their composites do not give any sound during deformation. They either do not debond or besides debonding stress some other factor also influences the number of signals.

Adhesion and Debonding

We investigated the fracture surface of specimens by electron microscopy in order to check if particles do or do not debond. In Fig. 4 we present two SEM micrographs recorded on the fracture surface of PP/CaCO₃ composites containing the filler with 21 μm particle size. The particles in Fig. 4a were coated with stearic acid, i.e. adhesion was weak, while the composite in Fig. 4b contained also MAPP resulting in strong adhesion. The surface of the particles is very clean and many signs of debonding are indicated in Fig. 4a. However, the number of detected signals was very small, in fact it decreased further compared to the neat filler. On the other hand, Fig. 4b indicates very good adhesion between the components, all the particles are covered by the polymer almost completely and no sign of debonding is seen in the figure. Nevertheless the number of signals was two orders of magnitudes larger. Obviously, SEM cannot give unambiguous proof about debonding and cannot explain the changes in the number of signals with adhesion or particle size.

Fig. 4 Effect of adhesion on debonding in PP/CaCO₃ composites containing particles with 21 μm size. a) poor adhesion (stearic acid), b) good adhesion (MAPP)

Another way to check debonding is the measurement of volume strain, i.e. the increase of specimen volume during measurement. The extent of volume increase was shown to increase with filler content in composites deforming mainly by debonding. The volume strain traces of composites containing the smallest CaCO₃ filler in increasing amounts is presented in Fig. 5. The composites contained also MAPP for improved interfacial adhesion. We can see that in spite of the small particle size and increased adhesion volume increases considerably and depends on filler content. These changes indicate that at least a part of the particles debond indeed, but sound is not emitted during the process. Obviously, particle size alone does not determine the development of sound and the strength of adhesion cannot explain it either.

Fig. 5 Volume increase during deformation in a PP/CaCO₃ composite containing the filler with 2.9 μm diameter and 20 wt% MAPP.

Energy of the Signals

During the evaluation of the results we analyzed several characteristics (total number of hits, average amplitude and energy) of the signals developed. Fig. 6a demonstrates the determination of the energy of the signals. The average of three measurements is used for the evaluation and the maximum of the distribution is used as the energy of the signal for comparison. We assumed that since debonding strength decreases with increasing particle size the energy of the signals should decrease as well, while increasing strength of adhesion should lead to an increase of energy.

Fig. 6 Determination of the energy of the signals (a) and the effect of particle size on energy in PP/CaCO₃ composites containing fillers with different sizes and MAPP (b).

The results do not support our expectations. The energy of the signals increase with increasing particle size considerably (Fig. 6b) and increased adhesion has the same effect. On the other hand, this might explain the fact that more signals are obtained in composites containing larger particles. As a consequence, we hoped to find a correlation between the energy of hits and the number of signals detected during testing. The results are presented in Fig. 7 for three series of composites. Average number of hits for entire series is plotted against the energy of the signals for composites containing glass beads, treated glass beads and CaCO₃. As the figure shows, an apparent correlation can be found between the two quantities. However, the correlation must be treated with the utmost care. The composites containing glass beads coated with stearic acid do not fit the general trend at all (full red point on the left). Also the large value obtained for the composites containing the largest CaCO₃ and MAPP biases the correlation considerably. The results indicate that an additional completely neglected factor may also influence sound generation. We assume that this factor is the debonded volume. If a high energy signal develops in a large volume the microphones can pick it up, but if the volume is small, the signal is weak and/or it is attenuated during propagation and does not reach the microphone. This would explain the lack of sound for small particles, which have excellent adhesion to the matrix, but sound is generated in a very small volume.

Fig. 7 Correlation between the energy of acoustic signals and the average number of hits in several composite series.

Properties and Consequences

Micromechanical deformation processes including debonding have a strong influence on the performance of the composite material. Failure is usually initiated by these local processes. As a consequence, information about their initiation and the characteristic values related to them may help to estimate the behavior of the material under practical conditions. Appropriate models may even help to predict failure initiation from the results of micromechanical testing. In order to prove the close correlation between the micromechanical processes accompanied by acoustic signals and the macroscopic properties of the composites, tensile yield stress is plotted against the characteristic stress detected at the development of the largest number of signals (peak of the derivative of cumulative hits, σ_{AE2} [8]) for practically all series of measurements. We can see that the correlation is valid irrespectively of the type of the filler or its surface modification. We must emphasize here that the characteristic value, σ_{AE2} , is larger than the initiation value, but smaller than the yield stress of the composite. This latter was proved to indicate the start of considerable irreversible plastic deformation [8]. Nevertheless, we can see that micromechanical deformation processes determine the macroscopic properties of composites indeed.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained on a large number of particulate filled composites containing fillers with a wide range of sizes and various surface modifications indicate that the dominating micromechanical deformation process is debonding in these materials. Not all debonding events generate sound; the number of acoustic signals detected by the microphones depends on particle size and on the strength of interfacial adhesion. These two factors determine the energy of the signals and the number of detected hits must depend also on the volume in which the signal is generated, but this

tentative explanation needs further study and proof. Although the acoustic emission technique has some limitations, it is a useful tool for the study of micromechanical deformation processes in heterogeneous polymers, especially if it is combined with other methods like volume strain measurements and SEM. The macroscopic properties and the performance of such composites are determined by the micromechanical deformation processes initiated around inclusions

Fig. 8 Correlation between the stress characterizing the maximum rate of debonding as determined by acoustic emission and the tensile yield stress of the composites.

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